

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN CONSCRIPTS.

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Communicative competence is an ability that allows conscripts to successfully solve communication problems and serves to provide many personal characteristics [1], its function is as follows :

establishing and maintaining psychological contact with various categories of citizens for a long time;

listen carefully to others, clearly explain your goals, and objectively evaluate the information you receive [2] ;

the ability to quickly perceive extralinguistic influences, i.e. the intonation of the interlocutor's words, the speed of speech, the rhythm of speech, etc.;

winning over others in difficult and controversial situations, etc.

From the above classifications, it can be seen that well-developed communicative skills are a psychological element that allows conscripts to manage the interaction situation and implement communicative plans. The sources also distinguish the structural elements of communicative competence formed in conscripts, and according to researcher A.G. Shestakova, they consist of the following [3] :

the language-related component - the formation of lexical and grammatical skills in a person;

speech component - the semantic and logical structure of words, the ability to argue one's position, continue the discussion, ask questions to the interlocutor, listen to him, and establish positive communication;

educational and cognitive component - the ability to work with information;

socio-cultural component - the culture of communication in a collaborative environment, the ability to listen to a partner, take one's own position in communication and form it;

moral and general cultural component - the ability to control oneself in different situations, respect for others, the ability to harmonize one's interests with the interests of others, etc. The above components are considered the specific foundations of successful interpersonal relationships in the activities of conscripts, and without them, it is unlikely to talk about the characterological qualities of a modern conscript.

interpersonal relationships is formed in several stages, namely, getting to know the interlocutors, friendships between the interlocutors, mutual support,

etc. [4] . Therefore, any competitions and competitions in society are carried out on the basis of friendly meetings, side by side activities. Such practices are of great importance for the good development of communicative competencies in conscripts.

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